

[研究文章 Research Article]

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First Record of the Genus *Zatypota* Förster, 1869 (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Pimplinae: *Polysphincta* Genus Group) from Taiwan and Notes on the Natural History of *Zatypota albicoxa* (Walker, 1874)

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Abstract. The genus *Zatypota* Förster, 1869 is recorded from Taiwan for the first time based on one female specimen of *Zatypota albicoxa* (Walker, 1874) reared from the host spider *Parasteatoda tepidariorum*. A short description of the parasitoid behavior of *Z. albicoxa* in Taiwan is provided.

Keywords: *Polysphincta* genus group, koinobiont, ectoparasitoid, Theridiidae, new records

Introduction

The *Polysphincta* group of genera within the Darwin wasps (family Ichneumonidae) are koinobiont ectoparasitoids of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) that primarily attach to and consume their host's body (Takasuka & Broad, 2024). The remarkable biology of this group has independently evolved alongside the tribe Ephialtini (Ichneumonidae, Pimplinae) and serves as a model system for studying host manipulation (Eberhard & Gonzaga, 2019; Takasuka & Broad, 2024). Among this group, the cosmopolitan genus *Zatypota* Förster, 1869 is the most diverse, comprising 52 species (Yu et al., 2016; Sobczak et al., 2019) that use theridiid spiders as hosts (Nielsen, 1923; Jiménez, 1987; Fitton et al., 1988; Gauld & Dubois, 2006; Takasuka & Broad, 2024).

The species *Z. albicoxa* (Walker, 1874) is widely distributed across the Holarctic and Oriental regions (Yu et al., 2016). This study represents the first record of both the species and the genus *Zatypota* in Taiwan, thereby filling a distribution gap for this group, along with observations on the parasitoidism and development of *Z. albicoxa* on its host, *Parasteatoda tepidariorum* (Koch, 1841) (Araneae, Theridiidae).

Materials and methods

The specimen was collected by the first author on February 23, 2024, on the Hemei Mountain Trail (24.955797 N, 121.534162 E), Xindian District, New Taipei City, Taiwan. One ichneumonid larva belonging to the *Polysphincta* genus group was collected along with its Theridiid spider host. The larva and host were kept in a plastic container (diameter 6cm) at room temperature (25°C) and a natural photoperiod (10 hours of light, 14 hours of darkness) until the ichneumonid eclosed. The behavior and developmental stages of the ichneumonid larva as well as the status of the host spider were recorded on a cellphone (Realme C2 2020). The adult wasp was identified using the keys of He et al. (1996) to genus and Matsumoto & Takasuka (2010) to species, and the host using Zhang et al. (2022) and Zehbi & Yousuf (2023). Morphological terms follow Broad et al. (2018) and measurements follow Kikuchi & Konishi (2021). The following abbreviations are used: **OD**: ocellar diameter; **POL**: postocellar line, minimum distance between lateral ocelli; **OOL**: ocular ocellar line, minimum distance between lateral ocelli and compound eyes; **T**: tergites.

Specimens were examined and measured with a LEICA S8APO microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany) and electronic micrometer (TEKFAR Inc., Taichung, Taiwan). Photos were taken with a LEICA DMC5400 camera and LEICA Z16 APO zoom system then combined with the LAS V4.13 auto-stacking system (Leica Microsystems). All figures were edited and arranged into figure plates with Adobe Illustrator CC and Photoshop CC (Adobe Systems Inc., San Jose, CA, USA). The voucher specimen from this study is deposited in the Taiwan Forestry Research Institute, Taipei, Taiwan (**TFRI**).

The abbreviations for type depositions in the synonymy list are presented as follows: **NHMUK**: Natural History Museum, London, UK; **PMJ**: Phyletisches Museum, Jena, Germany; **SEHU**: Laboratory of Systematic Entomology, Hokkaido University Museum, Sapporo, Hokkaido; **SMF**: Natur-Museum Senckenberg, Frankfurt am Main, Germany; **ZMB**: Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin, Germany.

Results

The collected Darwin wasp was identified as *Z. albicoxa* based on the adult female, and the host spider was identified as *Parasteatoda tepidariorum* (Koch, 1841) [大擬肥腹蛛] (Araneae, Theridiidae).

Observation on the development of the immature *Z. albicoxa*

The wasp larva was observed attached to the dorsobasal abdomen of the host spider. When collected, the host spider was able to move and weave normally (Fig. 1A). After 1 day, the host was killed and consumed by the wasp larva in a sequence starting from the abdomen and moving to other parts of the body within a few hours (Fig. 1B). After consuming the host, the wasp larva formed a white cocoon within a day (Fig. 1C). The color of the cocoon darkened to yellowish-brown after 10 days and the adult emerged after 11 days (Fig. 1D). The observed duration of the late instar larva and cocoon stages of *Z. albicoxa* was 13 days, summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1. Parasitoidism of *Zatyptota albicoxa* on the host spider *Parasteatoda tepidariorum*. A: *Z. albicoxa* larva attached to the dorsal-base abdomen of the host; B: larva consuming the host; C: cocoon of *Z. albicoxa*; D: eclosed female adult of *Z. albicoxa*.

Table 1. Timeline of *Zatyptota albicoxa* parasitoidism on host spider *Parasteatoda tepidariorum*

Date	Time	Observation
2024, Feb. 23	18:49	Parasited host spider collected.
2024, Feb. 24	15:18	Host spider dead, completely consumed by the wasp larva.
2024, Feb. 25	18:28	Wasp larva cocooned.
2024, Mar. 06	12:35	Wasp eclosed.

New record of the genus *Zatyptota* in Taiwan

Zatyptota Förster, 1869

多印姬蜂屬

Zatyptota Förster, 1869: 166. Type species: *Ichneumon percontatorius* Müller. Subsequent designation by Viereck (1914).
Polysphinctopsis Habermehl, 1917: 167. Type species: *Polysphincta eximia* Schmiedeknecht (= *Glypta albicoxa*). By monotypy.
Lycorinopsis Haupt, 1954: 110. Type species: *Lycorinopsis lombifer* Haupt (= *Ichneumon percontatorius* Müller). By original designation.

Diagnosis. The diagnosis is rephrased based on Matsumoto & Takasuka (2010). This genus can be distinguished from other genera of *Polysphincta* genus group by the combination of: pronotum with epomia present; mesoscutum polished and smooth, almost without seta (Fig. 2D); hind wing with distal abscissa of CU absent (Fig. 2B); metasomal T2–T4 with a flat or weakly convex central area surrounded by grooves with short longitudinal carinae (Fig. 2E); central area of T2 and T3 rhombic or transversely rhombic (Fig. 2E); propodeum typically with lateromedian longitudinal carinae and posterior transverse carina complete (Fig. 2D); ovipositor short.

Description. A detailed description of this genus was provided by Gauld & Dubois (2006).

Bionomics. This genus usually uses Theridiidae as hosts (Nielsen, 1923; Jiménez, 1987; Fitton et al., 1988; Gauld & Dubois 2006; Takasuka & Broad, 2024), with fewer records on Dictynidae (Howard, 1888). The records on Araneidae (Aubert, 1969; Constantineanu & Pisica, 1977), Agelenidae (Uchida, 1927; Aubert, 1969) and Tetragnathidae (Bignell, 1898; Morley, 1908; Schmiedeknecht, 1934; Aubert, 1969) are considered questionable (Gauld & Dubois, 2006).

Remarks. This is the first record of this genus in Taiwan.

Zatypota albicoxa (Walker, 1874)

白基多印姬蜂

(Fig. 2)

Glypta albicoxa Walker, 1874: 304. Holotype: ♀, Japan (NHMUK).

Pimpla colorata Rudow, 1883: 237. Lectotype: Unknown, France: Evreux (PMJ). Synonymized by Horstmann (1993).

Polysphincta eximia Schmiedeknecht, 1907: 1170. Lectotype: ♀, Germany (ZMB). Synonymized by Uchida (1940).

Polysphinctopsis eximia f. *nigriventris* Habermehl, 1917: 168. Holotype: ♀, Germany (SMF). Synonymized by Yu & Horstmann (1997).

Polysphincta japonica Uchida, 1927: 173. Lectotype: ♀, Japan: Toyoyama (SEHU). Synonymized by Uchida (1940).

Polysphinctopsis eximia f. *nigrithorax* Uchida, 1936: 54. Holotype: ♀, Kuriles: Kunashir Is., Yambetsu (SEHU). Synonymized by Uchida & Momoi (1958).

Diagnosis. This species can be diagnosed from other *Zatypota* species by: face lacking longitudinal ridge; flagellum segments more than 18 (Fig. 2B); hind femur not more than $6.0 \times$ as long as wide; postnervulus with CU not shorter than 2cu-a (Fig. 2B); and ovipositor upcurved (Fig. 2A).

Materials examined. TAIWAN. 1 ♀; New Taipei City, Xindian District, Hemeishan trail [和美山步道], 24.955797 N, 121.534162 E; 2024. II. 23 col., III. 06 eclosed; host: *Parasteatoda tepidariorum*; Y. K. Shih leg. (TFRI).

Short description based on Taiwanese specimen. General structures and coloration of the Taiwanese specimen align with the description of Matsumoto & Takasuka (2010) and are not repeated herein. The measurements and meristic counts of the Taiwanese specimen are as follows: head $1.7 \times$ as wide as long; POL/OD = 0.8; OOL/OD = 1.0; face $1.0 \times$ as wide as long; clypeus $1.8 \times$ as wide as long; malar space $0.6 \times$ as long as basal mandibular width; first flagellomere $5.3 \times$ as long as wide, $1.3 \times$ as long as second flagellomere; second flagellomere $4.0 \times$ as long as wide; mesoscutum $1.2 \times$ as long as wide; scutellum $1.0 \times$ as long as wide; fore wing with 2rs-m $0.2 \times$ as long as abscissa between 2rs-m and 2m-cu; distance between M&RS and 1cu-a $0.3 \times$ as long as 1cu-a; metasomal T1 $1.4 \times$ as long as wide, $1.2 \times$ as long as T2; T2 $0.9 \times$ as long as wide; fore femur $3.9 \times$ as long as wide; hind femur $5.1 \times$ as long as wide; hind tibia $10.9 \times$ as long as wide; hind first tarsomere $6.2 \times$ as long as wide, $1.5 \times$ as long as second tarsomere; ovipositor $0.5 \times$ as long as hind tibia; fore wing length 5.48 mm; palpal formula 4, 3; 26 flagellomere segments; basal hamuli 1, distal hamuli 5.

Chinese vernacular name. The Chinese vernacular names for this genus and species are adapted from the names provided by He et al. (1996) that are used in China. The genus name “多印姬蜂屬” (meaning “multiple imprinted ichneumonids”) likely refers to the tergites having a central area surrounded by grooves with short longitudinal carinae. The species name “白基多印姬蜂” is a direct translation of the original etymology of the specific name *albicoxa*, meaning “white coxa.”

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Figure 2. The Taiwanese specimen of *Zatyptota albicoxa* (female, TFRI). A: habitus in lateral view; B: habitus in dorsal view; C: head in anterior view; D: mesosoma in dorsal view; E: metasomal tergites 1–3.

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多印姬蜂屬（膜翅目：姬蜂科：瘤姬蜂亞科：嗜蛛姬蜂屬群）於臺灣之首次記錄暨白基多印姬蜂生物學觀察

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摘要：多印姬蜂屬 (*Zatypota* Förster, 1869) 以單隻自大擬肥腹蛛 (*Parasteatoda tepidariorum*) 飼養出的白基多印姬蜂 (*Zatypota albicoxa* (Walker, 1874)) 雌蟲首次記錄於臺灣。本研究亦提供臺灣白基多印姬蜂的簡短描述及生物學觀察。

關鍵字：嗜蛛姬蜂屬群、容性寄生、外擬寄生、姬蜂科、新紀錄